

of sodium and calcium salts, sodium acetate and calcium acetate were used in place of potassium acetate.

Analyses and Measurements: Manganese(III) content of salicylidene glycine complex was determined iodometrically. Total metal percentage was estimated by igniting the complexes and converting to sulphates. Nitrogen was estimated by Duma's method. C,H analyses were done at CDRI, Lucknow. Magnetic susceptibilities were obtained using the Gouy technique with $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as calibrant. IR spectra were run as KBr matrices.

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Kinetics and Mechanism of Osmium(VIII) Catalysed Oxidation of Dimethyl Sulphoxide with Potassium Hexacyanoferrate(III) in Aqueous Alkaline Medium

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THE reaction $\text{DMSO} - \text{Mn}^{3+}$ has been employed as a red-ox initiator for vinyl-polymerisation.¹ We have recently reported a kinetic study of DMSO-oxidation by Cr(VI) and Ce(IV) .² Recently we have communicated the kinetics of oxidation of DMSO by chloramine-T(CAT) in acid medium and OsO_4 catalysed oxidation of DMSO by CAT in alkaline medium.³ This present communication concerns with the oxidation of DMSO by potassium

hexacyanoferrate(III) in alkaline medium catalysed by OsO_4 .

Materials and Methods :

E. Merck (G. R. grade) sample of potassium hexacyanoferrate(III), sodium carbonate free sodium hydroxide, potassium chloride (BDH) AR grade and dimethyl sulphoxide (BDH) AR grade were employed. Osmium(VIII) solution was prepared from Osmium tetroxide. Aqueous solution of potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) was stored in dark amber coloured bottles to avoid photochemical reaction. The ionic strength was kept constant throughout the study by using 0.025 M KCl. The rate constants have been computed by the usual tangential method and are reproducible within 3% error.

Results and Discussion

The reaction was found to be first order in the substrate and first order in ferricyanide. The first order rate constant increases with increasing concentration of DMSO up to a limiting concentration 0.035 M of DMSO. Beyond this concentration, k_1 remains constant indicating zero order with respect to DMSO (Table 1).

TABLE 1
EFFECT OF VARYING SUBSTRATE CONCENTRATION
Ferricyanide = 0.00125 M, NaOH = 0.0025 M, KCl = 0.025 M,
 $\text{OsO}_4 = 3.9 \times 10^{-6}$ M, Substrate = DMSO. Temp. 35°C.

[Substrate] M	k_1 sec ⁻¹
0.00205	0.0001636
0.00402	0.000331
0.00717	0.0005155
0.035	0.001395
0.070	0.001727
0.140	0.001727
0.210	0.001727

In the concentration range where the order with respect to DMSO is zero it was decided to vary the ferricyanide concentration. Though it is expected that the first order rate constant should remain constant with increasing $[\text{Fe(CN)}_6^{3-}]$ to prove the first order nature with respect to ferricyanide, there is a decrease in the rate constant. This apparent decrease in rate may be attributed to the mass law effect. As the reaction product ferrocyanide is formed, it shifts the equilibrium towards ferricyanide and hence the observed retarding rate. This has been independently checked by performing a run with 0.00125 M of potassium ferrocyanide, where there was no reaction at all, confirming our reasoning that the observed retardation with increasing ferricyanide is only due to the mass law effect (Table 2).

TABLE 2
EFFECT OF VARYING FERRICYANIDE CONCENTRATION
NaOH=0.0025 M, DMSO=0.07 M, KCl=0.025 M,
OsO₄=3.9 × 10⁻⁶ M. Temp. 35°C,

[Ferricyanide] M	k ₁ sec ⁻¹
0.00125	0.001727
0.002	0.001394
0.003	0.0009892
0.004	0.0007963

Variation of alkali and Osmium (VIII) :

The order with respect to Osmium(VIII) is one. The first order rate constant increases with increasing concentration of Os(VIII). The order with respect to alkali is also unity. The rate constants at different concentrations of Os(VIII) and NaOH are reported in Tables 3 and 4.

TABLE 3
EFFECT OF VARYING ALKALI
Ferricyanide=0.00125 M, KCl=0.025 M, OsO₄=3.9 × 10⁻⁶ M,
DMSO=0.002 M. Temp. 35°C.

[NaOH] M	k ₁ sec ⁻¹
0.0025	0.0001636
0.005	0.000549
0.0075	0.000620
0.01	0.000752

TABLE 4
EFFECT OF VARYING Os(VIII)
DMSO=0.07 M, NaOH=0.0025 M, KCl=0.025 M,
Ferricyanide=0.00125 M, Temp. 35°C

[Os(VIII)] × 10 ⁶ M	k ₁ sec ⁻¹
3.12	0.001189
3.9	0.0017
5.85	0.00239
7.8	0.00376

The variation of ionic strength was studied by varying the concentration of KCl. Increasing concentration of KCl increased the rate. Effect of KBr is same as KCl. But KI enhances the rate slightly (Table 5).

TABLE 5
EFFECT OF VARYING IONIC STRENGTH
NaOH=0.0025 M, OsO₄=3.9 × 10⁻⁶ M, DMSO=0.002 M,
Ferricyanide=0.00125 M. Temp. 35°C

Salt	Conc ⁿ . M	k ₁ sec ⁻¹
	0.025	0.000163
	0.05	0.000219
KCl	0.075	0.000267
	0.1	0.000292
KBr	0.025	0.0001498
KI	0.025	0.000198

It is pertinent to point out here that the reaction between DMSO and Ferricyanide in the pH range 6.85 to 9.4 does not take place.

Mechanism :

In accordance with the observed experimental data it is possible to postulate the following mechanism for substrate concentrations at and below 0.035 M.

The above mechanism clearly explains the first order dependence on substrate, Ferricyanide, [OH⁻] and Os(VIII). Such unit dependence on substrate, oxidant, alkali and catalyst was earlier observed in Se(IV) oxidations* involving the formation of Se(V) as an intermediate in the reversible rate determining step followed by its fast oxidation to Se(VI) by Os(VIII); the catalyst being generated in a subsequent fast oxidation of Os(VII) by hexacyanoferrate(III).

In the concentration range above 0.035 M of the substrate the order with respect to alkali and hexacyanoferrate(III) is each one but the order with respect to substrate is zero. This can be visualised by the mechanism

The above mechanism suggests a possible complex formation between hexacyanoferrate(III) and Os(VIII). Formation of such complex has also been postulated previously by Mushran⁶ and Muralikrishna⁶.

In accordance with the mechanism the rate law at high concentrations of the substrate takes the form

$-d[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]/dt = k[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}][\text{OH}^-][\text{Os}(\text{VIII})]$ and at lower concentrations of the substrate the rate law becomes

$-d[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]/dt = k(S)[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}][\text{OH}^-]$
[Os(VIII)]

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Studies on Azido Complexes of Cobalt :

Part I

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ONLY a few transition metal ions are known to form azido complexes. It is only with cobalt as the central metal atom do we have a variety of complexes of the type MA_3B^1 , $MA_2B_2^2$, $M(AA)_2B_2$ and $MA_3B_3^3$ where A is a unidentate group such as ammonia, AA is a bidentate group such as ethylenediamine⁴, 1, 10 orthophenanthroline⁵, 2, 2' bipyridyl⁶, acetylaceton⁷, and B is the azido group.

Of the bidentate ligands notable exceptions are dimethylglyoxime and biguanide. The synthesis of azido complexes of cobalt with dimethylglyoxime has been reported recently⁸. In this communication we report the preparation and characterisation of the pair cis and trans diazido bis biguanide cobalt(III) azide.

Experimental

Trans $Co[(big\ H)_2(N_3)_2]N_3 \cdot H_2O$ was prepared by reacting a saturated solution of $trans[Co(big\ H)_2Cl_2]Cl^9$ with an excess of solid sodium azide in a water bath kept at 60°-80° for half an hour. The solution is cooled and kept in a refrigerator overnight when orange crystals separate out. The crystals are filtered, washed with rectified spirit; the product is then recrystallised from water and dried in air.

The starting material for the preparation of $cis[Co(big\ H)_2(N_3)_2]N_3 \cdot H_2O$ is $cis[Co(big\ H)_2(NH_2)_2]Cl_2$ which was prepared by the method of Dutta & Sircar¹⁰. The compound was suspended in water air was passed through it for several hours and warmed on a water bath at 60°-80° for about an hour, and then treated with excess of solid sodium azide for half an hour at 60°-80°. The resulting solution was left in refrigerator over night and filtered to collect the violet crystals. The crystals were washed with water and alcohol and recrystallised from water and then air dried.

Cobalt was determined by converting it to cobalt sulphate and weighing as anhydrous cobalt sulphate. Total nitrogen was estimated by Duma's Method. Labile azide which constitutes one-third of the total azide was estimated by precipitating as silver azide and weighing. Analytical data are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1
CHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF THE COMPLEXES

Compound	Co	N	N ₃ ⁻
Trans $[Co(big\ H^+)_2(N_3)_2]N_3 \cdot H_2O$	14.54	65.69	10.37 % Calcd.
	14.10	64.80	9.80 % Found.
Cis $[Co(big\ H^+)_2(N_3)_2]N_3 \cdot H_2O$	14.54	65.69	10.37 % Calcd.
	14.00	66.00	10.57 % Found.

Results and Discussion

The visible and U. V spectra was determined in a Beckman Spectrophotometer Model D. U. In aqueous media the cis compound has two peaks at 296 nm ($\epsilon_M=316$) and 508 nm ($\epsilon_M=168$). The trans compound has also two bands at 350 nm ($\epsilon_M=208$) and at 482 nm ($\epsilon_M=208$). For both compounds there is no evidence of any splitting of the bands in the visible region.

The i.r. spectra were recorded in a Beckman I.R. 20 in KBR pellets.

The bending mode $\delta(N_3)$ and the asymmetric stretch of co-ordinated azides $\nu(N_3)$ as lie in the regions 626-677 cm^{-1} and 2037-2092 cm^{-1} respectively for azide cobaltamine complexes⁴. The symmetric $\nu(N_3)S$ stretch¹¹, when it is observed as in $MoCl_4(N_3)_2$, occurs in the region 1190-1260 cm^{-1} .

On the basis of these the following assignments if i.r. bands may be made and is given in Table 2 in which v.s (denotes very strong, S means strong) and m indicates medium.

The assignment of $\nu(N_3)S$ is doubtful as a band at 1255 (m) is also observed in $[Co(big\ H)_2OH \cdot H_2O]SO_4 \cdot 2.5H_2O$.